

6. Refinement

Crystal data, data collection and structure refinement details are summarized in Table 2. All aromatic hydrogens and hydrogen atoms of the CH groups were placed in their expected calculated positions ($C-H = 0.95 \text{ \AA}$) and refined as riding with $U_{iso}(H) = 1.2U_{iso}(C)$. Methyl H atoms were placed in their expected calculated positions ($C-H = 0.98 \text{ \AA}$) and refined as rotating groups with $U_{iso}(H) = 1.5U_{eq}(C)$. Hydrogen atoms of the water molecules were assigned based on the difference-Fourier map, and the O–H distances and the H–O–H angles were constrained using DFIX (O–H = $0.84 \text{ \AA}$) and DANG (H–H = $1.34 \text{ \AA}$) instructions. The hydrogen H atom of the solvent methanol molecule was assigned based on the difference-Fourier map, and the O–H distance was constrained using a DFIX (O–H = $0.96 \text{ \AA}$) instruction.

Funding information

The work was supported by H2020-MSCA-RISE-2016 Project 73422.

References

- Dolomanov, O. V., Bourhis, L. J., Gildea, R. J., Howard, J. A. K. & Puschmann, H. (2009). *J. Appl. Cryst.* **42**, 339–341.
- Garcia, H. C., Diniz, R. & de Oliveira, L. F. C. (2011). *Open Crystallogr. J.* **4**, 30–39.
- Gural'skiy, I. A., Golub, B. O., Shylin, S. I., Ksenofontov, V., Shepherd, H. J., Raithby, P. R., Tremel, W. & Fritsky, I. O. (2016). *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.* pp. 3191–3195.
- Gural'skiy, I. A., Shylin, S. I., Golub, B. O., Ksenofontov, V., Fritsky, I. O. & Tremel, W. (2016). *New J. Chem.* **40**, 9012–9016.
- Gütlich, P. & Goodwin, H. A. (2004). *Top. Curr. Chem.*, Vol. 234, pp. 233–235. Berlin, Heidelberg, New York: Springer.
- Muñoz, M. C. & Real, J. A. (2011). *Coord. Chem. Rev.* **255**, 2068–2093.
- Niel, V., Muñoz, M. C., Gaspar, A. B., Galet, A., Levchenko, G. & Real, J. A. (2002). *Chem. Eur. J.* **8**, 2446–2453.
- Rigaku OD (2015). *CrysAlis PRO*. Rigaku Oxford Diffraction, Yarnton, England.
- Sheldrick, G. M. (2008). *Acta Cryst. A* **64**, 112–122.
- Sheldrick, G. M. (2015). *Acta Cryst. C* **71**, 3–8.

